

RESOURCE-SAVING TECHNOLOGIES - AN EFFECTIVE FACTOR OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTION

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Abstract: The article provides an overview of currently relevant resource conservation and determination of the optimal ratio of resources in Uzbekistan. A comparative analysis is given of most of the technologies used in domestic agriculture that have increased resource and energy intensity. The main elements of resource-saving technologies, allowing to reduce the level of total costs and ensure high quality of products, are presented.

Key words: resource-saving technologies, minimization of soil cultivation, traditional plowing, soil erosion, no-till plowing, mulch seeding, no-till.

Аннотация. В статье приведен обзор актуального в настоящее время ресурсосбережения и определения оптимального соотношения ресурсов в Узбекистане. Дан сравнительный анализ большинства используемых в отечественном земледелии технологий, обладающих повышенной ресурсоэнергоёмкостью. Представлены основные элементы ресурсосберегающих технологий, позволяющие снизить уровень совокупных затрат и обеспечить высокое качество продукции.

Ключевые слова: ресурсосберегающие технологии, минимизация обработок почвы, традиционная вспашка, эрозия почвы, безотвальная вспашка, мульчированный посев, нуле вая обработка.

Annotasiya. Maqolada hozirda dolzarb bo'lgan resurslarni tejash va O'zbekistonda resurslarning optimal nisbatini aniqlash masalalari ko'rib chiqilgan. Davlatimiz qishloq xo'jaligida qo'llaniladigan resurs va energiya intensivligini oshirgan texnologiyalarning qiyosiy tahlili berilgan. Jami xarajatlar darajasini

pasaytirish va mahsulotning yuqori sifatini ta'minlash imkonini beruvchi resurslarni tejovchi texnologiyalarning asosiy elementlari keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: resurstejamkor texnologiyalar, tuproqqa ishlovni minimallashtirish, an'anaviy shudgorlash, tuproq eroziyasi, ag'darmastan shudgorlash, mulchalash, nol ishlov berish.

Conservation agriculture system provides the opportunity to increase production efficiency while reducing costs and minimizing damage to the environment through the use of resource-saving technologies and precision farming. Resource-saving technologies are a set of agricultural practices performed in a certain sequence, aimed at satisfying the requirements of crop biology and obtaining a high yield of a given quality. The main elements of resource-saving technologies are biologization of crop rotations, minimization of soil cultivation, rational use of fertilizers, ameliorants and modern plant protection products, application of new high-yielding varieties, as well as the use of new generation agricultural machinery [1]. It is proposed to abandon plowing, to preserve residues on the soil surface, to use crop rotations that include profitable crops and crops that improve soil fertility, an integrated approach to pest and disease control, and to use high-quality seeds applicable to these technologies.

A comparative description of soil cultivation systems, taking into account the specifics of seeding technology and impact on the soil, is presented in the table.

Table 1

Comparative characteristics of soil cultivation systems

Tillage system	Features of sowing	Impact on soil	Characteristic features of the technology
Traditional (using moldboard)	After plowing with using moldboard	Soil erosion	It is carried out on well-cultivated and prepared soil for sowing, using moldboard and non-moldboard plowing and a number of small soil

			cultivations. The technology is intensive and costly.
Moldboard less	After plowing without moldboard	Soil erosion	There are no plant remains on the soil surface. The soil is easily subject to water and wind erosion. Increased moisture evaporation is observed, and the structure and fertility of the soil deteriorate. It is used in the absence of chemical plant protection products.
Minimum	Mulched sowing	Soil compaction	It is carried out on finely tilled soil with the creation of a mulching layer of stubble. The mulching layer reduces moisture evaporation and eliminates the risk of water and wind erosion. Fuel costs are reduced. Soil fertility is increased, structure is improved
No-till	Direct seeding	Improvement in soil condition is observed	Direct seeding is carried out on an uncultivated field, refusing all types of mechanical soil cultivation. Sowing is carried out while preserving the stubble and evenly scattering chopped straw. Stubble helps to retain snow and accumulate moisture. There is no susceptibility to water and wind erosion. Soil fertility increases. Retains moisture, saves fuel, preserves the environment

Resource-saving technologies provide:

- improving soil conditions for the development of agricultural crops and reducing the risk of erosion;
- labor savings;
- reduction in fuel consumption;
- high efficiency of field work.

The following principles form the basis of resource-saving technologies:

- minimization or elimination of mechanical tillage;
- preservation of plant residues on the soil surface;
- the use of crop rotations that include, along with the most economical crops, crops that improve soil fertility;
- integrated approach to pest and plant disease control;
- use of high-quality seeds that are responsive to resource-saving technologies.

Resource-saving technologies, unlike traditional ones, provide for two systems of soil cultivation - minimum and zero. Below are the main technological operations for moldboard, minimum and no-tillage [2].

Traditional soil cultivation	Minimum tillage	No-tillage
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • stubble cultivation; • application of mineral fertilizers; • plowing; • harrowing; • cultivation; • sowing • herbicide treatment; • fungicide treatment; • insecticide treatment; • harvesting 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • application of mineral fertilizers; • cultivation; • sowing; • herbicide treatment; • insecticide treatment; • harvesting 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • sowing with application of mineral fertilizers; • herbicide treatment; • insecticide treatment; • harvesting

It is recommended to introduce resource-saving agriculture technologies, as they will ensure sustainable development of agricultural production and increase the competitiveness of the agro-industrial complex. These technologies achieve savings in fuel and lubricants by two to three times, labor costs by up to three times, expenses on repair and maintenance of equipment are reduced by more than half, soil fertility is preserved, and the environmental situation is improved [3].

Conclusion. A comparative analysis showed that most of the technologies used in domestic agriculture have increased resource and energy intensity. In the context of high prices for fuels and lubricants, spare parts for agricultural machinery, fertilizers and pesticides, producers need to switch to resource-saving methods that reduce the level of total costs and ensure high quality products.

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